

A THREE DIMENSIONAL CRACK ANALYSES IN A SANDWICH SPECIMEN UNDER FLEXURAL LOADING

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SUMMARY

Extending the two dimensional cracked problem which has been studied under plane strain conditions using the J integral evaluation in sandwich specimens under flexural loading, a three dimensional analysis is performed. A numerical method using a commercial finite element program and creating a code in order to confront the singular three dimensional crack problem, has been implemented. An investigation of the numerical results for the J integral of a crack into the core of a sandwich specimen is also included in this study.

Keywords: Three dimensional crack analysis, Virtual crack method, J integral, Sandwich specimen, Finite element method, Gaussian integration.

INTRODUCTION

Rigid polymeric foams and low density foams often used as core materials in sandwich structures, they are receiving increasing attention in nowadays. Mechanical properties of cellular foams have been summarized by Gibson and Ashby [1]. Ford and Gibson [2] studied the uniaxial strength of cellular materials and Torquado S, Gibiansky LV, Silva MJ. [3] investigated the effective mechanical and transport properties of cellular bodies. Experimental investigation have been introduced by N. Kulkarni, H. Mahfuz, S. Jeelani, and L. A. Carlsson [4]. Zenkert [5] studied the mode-II and mixed-mode crack propagation of PVC cellular foam. Failure mode maps for foam core sandwich beams have been studied by Triantfillou, and Gibson, [6]. Different approaches for three dimension analyses using energy quantities as J integral or energy release rate have been studied by different investigators. G. Fernlund, D. McCammond and J.K. Spelt [7] applied the J integral in order to study the cracking delaminating of curved laminates. Energy release rate and J-integral configurations for a three dimensional studies are also presented in [8, 9]. Methods for calculating stress intensity factors for cracked two and three dimensional bodies as the virtual crack closure technique are developed in [10-12]. For the interfacial crack problem concerning biomaterials, a method has been proposed in [13]. A method used also in three dimensional analyses is the stiffness derivative finite element technique [14]. In literature a comprehensive description to model and simulate cracking effects using two dimensional (2d) or three dimensional (3d) finite elements implementation in a huge area of applications can be found in [15]. In this study based on the virtual advance method [8, 15], we try to simulate the fatigue crack propagation in the core of flexural loaded sandwich beams implemented a three dimensional code.

DESCRIPTION OF THE PROBLEM

The purpose of the present work is to numerically investigate the fatigue crack propagation in the core of sandwich beams under flexural loading, using a three dimensional model. The construction of the 2d model, the experimental data, the physical properties of the beam, the materials which is made the beam, the boundary conditions and the meshing are explicitly described in [10]. The non coincided point between the 2d and the 3d models is that in this study a less dense model in the brick type version is used than it for the two dimensional approach [10, 11]. It has to be mentioned that the strongly non linear behavior of the 2d model is increasing much further in the 3d one, as a result of the presence of the dimensional contact elements between the crack flanks. Using the finite element method in a three dimensional formulation and assuming Linear Fracture Mechanics, the J values are evaluated by means of a numerical evaluation of the J-volume integral. The geometric parameters were used in order to simulate different locations of the crack tips and different crack lengths, are seen in Figure 1 and presented in Table 2. The material constants are seen in Table 1.

Figure 1: The model of beam and the geometric characteristics

Table 1: Geometrical characteristics of the beam.

Length of beam, L	228.6 mm
Width of beam, b	63.5 mm
Width of upper and lower layer t_1, t_2	2.28 mm
Width of core t	12.7mm

Table 2 :Elasticity constants of the beam.

Material	? (N/mm^2 , or, MPa)	Poisson ratio ?
Composite Sheet isotropic glass reinforced resin (upper and lower layers)	16300	0.3
Core material PVC foam , R75 by DIAB [11]	80	0.4

BASIC THEORY

Surface and Volume J integral.

At first it is introduced the domain integral of J in two dimensions. In the absence of thermal loads, body forces and crack-faces tractions, the J domain integral is given by [12]:

$$J = \int_A \left[\mathbf{s}_{ij} \frac{J u_j}{\partial x_i} - w \mathbf{d}_{li} \right] \frac{\partial q}{\partial x_i} dA ; \quad i, j = 1, 2, \quad (1)$$

where A is the integration domain around the crack tip, u_{ij} is the displacements of the nodes inside the integrated area, s_{ij} the stresses of nodes inside the domain, w the potential energy per thickness unit and volume. The quantity q is a mathematical quantity which will be introduced in sequence and it is used to normalize the numerical expression.

For a three dimensional approximation it is necessary to convert the equation (1) into a volume integral [12]. In order to facilitate the numerical, evaluation from equation (1) and taking into consideration reference [12], the volume integral takes the form:

$$J(n) \approx \frac{\bar{J} \Delta L}{\int_{\Delta L} q(n, r_0) \mathbf{d}}, \quad (2)$$

$$\bar{J} \mathbf{DL} = \int_V \left\{ \left[\mathbf{s}_{ij} \frac{J u_j}{\partial x_i} - w \mathbf{d}_{li} \right] \frac{\partial q}{\partial x_i} - \int_{S_+ + S_-} \mathbf{s}_{2j} \frac{J u_j}{\partial x_i} q dG \right\}, \quad (3)$$

where $J(n)$, is the point wise value of J as it varies generally along the crack front , \bar{J} is the value of J in a finite segment of the crack front, \mathbf{n} is the unit vector which is tangent to the crack front and defines the direction along which we will evaluate numerically the volume integral. The second term of equation (3) depicts the contribution of the mutually traction of the crack flanks in the evaluation of J integral. The above volume integral will be estimated by means of numerical Gaussian integration of J integral, and the whole technique will be unfolded in the follow part of our study.

Figure 2. A segment of the three dimensional crack front and the surrounding surfaces which constitute the additional integral Volume of the segment.

It is observed from Figure 2 that the integration volume consists of the inner surface (S_0) the outer one (S_1) and the linear segments (S_+ , and S_-) in front of the crack tip which are the contacted parts of the crack flanks.

There is no necessity to follow the hollow cylindrical solid scheme, but this solid type has many advantages when it is built a code for the 3d Volume integration using a cylindrical local coordinate system along the crack front.

The Finite Element Approach.

The prerequisites of a Finite Element implementation of a 3dimensional cracked model with the non linear characteristics when using contact elements are unlimited. The more elements are used the more computational power is needed, and the more possibilities has the system to crash. A typical 3d finite element model is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: The typical used three dimensional Finite Element model

For the above described reasons the final FE model which is proposed for the calculations has a moderate approach concerning the density of the mesh. Additional concern must be taken of the designed regions-areas which produce the Volume of the solid part. As it can be seen in Figure 3 the crack tips and the crack flanks are surrounded by a nearly rectangular area which is much denser with a fine mesh than the other regions of the model.

An analogue procedure with that described in [11] of the energy domain integral for the 2d problem must be followed in the 3d model. The volume of integration must be defined in terms of the sum of the sub-volumes for each element which constitute components of the volume of integration. This must also be valid for each brick element along the width (b) of the beam. Furthermore a function q very similar to the shape functions of an isoparametric Finite Element formulation must be defined [16]. This must be done for a smooth arithmetic stability situation. This results an extremely complication in the analyses and in the design strategy of the proposal study as it will be developed in the next sections. In addition the function q 'manipulates' the influence of the elementary crack tip advance as it takes different values for each node for every pertinent element within the integrated volume.

The q function within an element can be interpolated as follows:

$$q(x_i) = \sum_{I=1}^n N_I q_I, \quad (4)$$

where: N_I is the shape function of the brick element, n is the number of nodes and q_I is the nodal values for each node given by:

$$q = \frac{\Delta x_1}{\Delta a}, \quad (5)$$

where Δx_1 is the virtual node advance for a predefined elementary crack advance Δa .

The spatial derivative of q is given by:

$$\frac{\partial q}{\partial x_i} = \sum_{l=1}^n \sum_{k=1}^3 \frac{\partial N_l}{\partial \mathbf{x}_k} \frac{\partial \mathbf{x}_k}{\partial x_i} q_l, \quad (6)$$

where n is the number of nodes per element, q_l is the nodal values of q (equation 5), N_l are the element shape functions and \mathbf{x}_k are the natural or parametric coordinates of the element.

In the absence of thermal strains, path depended plastic strains, and body forces within the integration volume, the discretized form of the volume integral is as follows:

$$J = \sum_V \sum_{p=1}^m \left\{ \left[\left(\mathbf{s}_{ij} \frac{\partial u_j}{\partial x_i} - w \mathbf{d}_{li} \right) \frac{\partial q}{\partial x_i} \right] \det \left(\frac{\partial x_j}{\partial \mathbf{x}_k} \right) \right\} w_p - \sum_{crack-faces} \left(\mathbf{s}_{2i} \frac{\partial u_j}{\partial x_1} q \right) w_p, \quad (7)$$

where m is the number of Gaussian points per element, and w_p are the weighting factors. The quantities within $\{ \}_p$ are evaluated at the Gaussian points. The second term in (7) represents the contact stresses, and this quantity affects equation (7) as soon as the crack faces are coming in contact during the imposed load. In this study the results based on equation (7) without the last term of the 3d FE model, will be compared with equivalent data from the 2d J domain integral [11]. The w quantity represents the potential energy of the element, and the term $\det()$ represents the Jacobian determination. This term arises since we have an incremental transformation of the coordinate system which is located at the crack tip, parallel to the x -axis.

THE FINITE ELEMENT SOLUTION

Strategy of meshing design and 3d construction

The design of a finite element mesh and especially the construction of a beam under flexural loading with a crack enclosed in the compressive area have many difficulties. The most common is that we have to ensure for the crack lips not to penetrate each other. This is the reason we insert contact elements valid for 2d and 3d analyses and avoid the undesirable situation above. This has an additional cost in the consumption of computational power and the demands on computational resources because of the inserted nonlinearity. This problem becomes more complicated when we get involved with 3d analyses. For this reason it is of great importance to approach the problem with a specific way. A problem appeared in the analysis is the specification of the terms in relation (5). Because the value of q has to be unit at the midside nodes of the wedge element and zero at the planes $s-t$ for $r=\pm 1$ (Figure 4). An additional prerequisite of a 3d analysis is the manipulation of many matrix calculations involved in relation (7) (i.e. the inversion of the Jacobian determinant).

Because from the 3d mesh we may have the highly time-consumable solution for the 3d model, we have to find a way to remesh a small relatively area around the crack tip, and determine the terms described in equation (7) without solving again the model. This is the problem that we will focus in the following paragraphs.

The term $\frac{\partial}{\partial a}$

This term gives the quantity q_i which is a factor in relation (4). We establish this term by means of linear interpolation between the crack length, the elementary advanced crack length and the coordinate in x axis, keeping constant the variation in the other two axes, as we study the planar virtual crack advance along x axis. In order to proceed our study we have to recognise three areas of the model around the crack tip and shown in Figures 5 and 6. The layer in z axis on which lays the wedge element, the internal area in which lay the singular elements, and finally the area in which lay the nodes that we will give a displacement. This is the area between zone A and zone B (Figure 5). As the area around the crack tip has no specific geometry (detail 'A' in Figure 3, Figure 5), we have to define a ring where the position of the nodes within it, will be kept constant (zone B). This will be done also for the nodes of the singular elements (zone A). In other words we keep these groups of nodes constant and move the rest nodes of the zones A and B (Figure 5). As for time saving it is not intended to remesh the finite element model for every crack advance, it is chosen an appropriate function which interpolates the new global coordinate in the x-axis with the previous one, for every node between the zones A and B, given by:

$$x'_c = x_c \frac{a + \Delta a}{a}, \quad (8)$$

where x'_c is the new coordinate in x axis with respect to the crack tip which is the origin, a is the crack length and Δa is the incremental of the crack front. If we take $\Delta x_1 = x'_c - x_c$ and divide it by Δa we have from (5) the quantity q_i for each node. It is obvious from Figure 4 that keeping constant the nodes laying in planes $r = \pm 1$, it is obtained $q_i = 0$.

Figure 4: The typical 15 node wedge element. and the orientation of the local coordinate system.

Figure 5: A closer look at the region around the crack tip referred as 'A' in Figure 3.

In the proposed analysis it is studied the planar propagation of the crack, thus the other two spatial derivatives of q in respect to the global y and z coordinates are supposed to be zero. In Figure 6 are shown the appropriately selected nodes which lay between the zones A, B. The elements that correspond to the appropriately selected nodes above and give the terms in are shown in Figure 7.

Figure 6: The selected nodes between zone A and zone B.

Figure 7: The selected elements which carry the nodes between zone A and zone B.

The radius of the external zone namely the number of nodes will be selected for the calculation of the J volume integral, since the volume has to be independent from the selection of his outer and inner boundary surfaces, is an intuitive matter. It must be taken into account the density of the 3d finite element model near this crack tip and the results of two sequentially runs must converge. The larger selected area is, the more computational time and the more consumption of computational resources is needed. It has to be noticed that because of the planar behaviour of the analyses the selected nodes along the crack face remain the same. In case of a non linear derivation of the crack front in respect to the z axis we should change for every brick element the selected nodes.

CONCLUSIONS AND DISCUSSION

Taking into consideration the proposed analysis, the results for the J integral and for different crack lengths are given in Figure 8. Finally from our analysis it results that:

Figure 8: J integral values for different crack length.

- As the 3d finite element model is less dense than the 2d one, the values for the J integral may have differences. This will be confronted with parallel programming techniques applied in a fine 3d mesh in the thickness direction.
- From the proposed analysis we may consider different approximations for the shape of the crack front as it could be for example a planar curve or in general a curve in space.
- The distance of the crack flank from the upper face of the core plays a significant role to the whole study, as it affects both the stress intensity factors and the value of J integral.
- In the present study a complex field of stresses arises, and this gives an advantage to energy methods of analyzing the problem compared to the conventional calculations of the stress intensity factors.

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